

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D2.4 Report on inter-ecosystem projects and best practices exchanged

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The INTEGER interregional learning process started with the study visits. During these a number of objectives were achieved:

1. The project consortium could learn about the main features (key actors, companies, social innovators, entrepreneurs), existing or prior networking and collaborative dynamics within each regional innovation ecosystem;
2. They could establish direct interactions with the key regional stakeholders and learn from a number of relevant initiatives that had been previously selected following the project set of criteria (these are explained in section 2.1 below);
3. Interpersonal, inter-regional, interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaborations were formed between the consortium partners and the communities in the regions, and very important among the actors in each of the regions. The project has paved the way to ignite the bonding among key partners that did not know yet and which connection is crucial for the development of the ecosystem; and
4. Finally, the study visits helped to enhance project promotion within the regions.

The study visits followed the principle of cross-sectoral collaboration. The quadruple helix model brought together stakeholders from different fields and will be a starting point for as well cooperation inside the regions as for interregional cooperation. **Inter-regions study visits** put in contact key social and digital business innovators from the three regions.

The visits are important for the consortium, to define a common understanding of innovation and relevant stakeholder groups. But it is also important to see what different stakeholder groups define as innovative and what type of mechanisms are existing in the regions, that helps to improve innovation.

The next step of the interregional learning process was **the key stakeholders event**, the first event promoted between regional stakeholders in the INTEGER project. A first opportunity to start a conversation and engage directly with the main players of the regional ecosystems. This would also give the INTEGER partners the opportunity to benefit from these stakeholders' contributions and to kickstart a **Col·laborathon** that aimed to engage along the project stakeholders from the social innovation 3Helix in the sector of healthy living and well-being.

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SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

4H	Quadruple Helix (Academia, Business, Civil Society and Public Administration)
AHA	Active Healthy Ageing
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
GAS	Germany, Austria, Switzerland
I2Cat	Innovations to Catalonia
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
KPT	Krakow Technology Park
LL	Living Lab
LOI	Letter of Intent
MLHSA	Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SIG	Special Interest Group
SMEs	Small and Medium Sized Enterprises
SOAR	Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, and Results
T	Task
UJ	Jagiellonian University
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work-Package

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

The deliverable titled "Report on Inter-Ecosystem Projects and Best Practices Exchange" encapsulates INTEGER's core objective of fostering collaboration, mutual learning and inter-regional exchange across diverse cultural, background, regional dynamics and innovation styles.

This report delves into the exposure of stakeholders to the project's spectrum of three innovation ecosystems (Catalonia, Hamburg and Krakow), elucidating varied approaches in bridging gaps between distinct forms of innovation, including social, technological and business-driven endeavours.

It outlines best practices derived from the exchange, underlying the cultivation of a dynamic environment conducive to cross-cultural learning and innovation synergies within the INTEGER project. This document serves as a comprehensive record of insights and strategies gleaned from inter-ecosystem interactions during the first half of the project duration.

2 REGIONAL STUDY VISITS

The responsible people at each regional colocation mapped, selected, contacted and invited a group of key stakeholders from the quadruple helix (4H) spectrum to participate in INTEGER's Regional Study visits as one of the first actions to . The aim was to organise the team up with them for the project duration to accomplish the objectives and activities planned;

The three planned regional study visits had several objectives:

1. To learn from inspirational cases of social/business innovations already in place or under development in each of the regions;
2. To identify the main challenges of quadruple helix collaboration and co-creation mechanisms;
3. To start collecting ideas for the INTEGER 4H¹ comprehensive model;
4. To start identifying Minimum Viable Products and Services that could be later worked on in later stages of the project (e.g. the col-laborathons) to test the bilateral collaborative approach from the social-driven innovation and the business innovation side; and
5. To begin building or reinforcing 4H committed and interested communities at three levels. Within the context of each of the regions, among the three regions and at EU level (preparing the ground for the constitution of the INTEGER EU Col-laboratory on Health and Wellbeing in September 2023).

In each of the three regions, key social and digital business innovators, who play a significant role and are vital actors in healthy living, active ageing policy and social exclusion areas were going to put in contact to exchange and co-think together on the above-mentioned objectives.

¹ Quadruple Helix (Academia, Business, Civil Society and Public Administration)

2.1 Criteria to select inspirational cases

A number of criteria were defined by the consortium partners in order to identify and select inspirational cases that could show the tapestry of opportunities and untap and reflect the main features of the three innovation ecosystems in the regions:

1. Social innovations (emerging or more consolidated) focused on the field of health and wellbeing;
2. Selection of committed stakeholders from the mapping done by the partners of each region;
3. Covering one of the five topics identified within the wider field of Health and Wellbeing, these have served as a backbone for the three study visits and the challenges for the model event and the Col·laborathons:
 - a. Ageing (e.g. Senior Lab)
 - b. Pollution & healthy cities (e.g. Healthy Urban Generator by Bax & Company)
 - c. Nutrition (e.g. IrsiCaixa)
 - d. Social/laboral inclusion
 - e. Physical exercise (e.g. Biwel)
4. Balanced representation in terms of gender and type of actors from each or across the four helices:
 - a. public entities
 - b. business (e.g. Cluster Agency GWHH GmbH, Phillips),
 - c. academia
 - d. civil society organisations (e.g. Mein Lido)
 - e. Or the interconnections between some of these (e.g. Working Group Sustainable City Health)
5. Social-driven and business driven approaches depicted

2.2 Catalanian Study Visit

In the preparation phase of the study visit, the Catalanian project partners held a couple of information sessions with key stakeholders from the quadruple helix, to inform about the vision of INTEGER and to get them involved.

First information and co-creating session was held physically at the i2Cat Foundation offices on December 13th, 2022, where we invited potential stakeholders that some of them were already participating at the Catalonia Col·laboratory since around one year before. Catalonia Col·laboratory is a local initiative promoted by the Catalanian Government and executed by i2Cat. The Health and Wellbeing Catalanian Collaboratory aims to create a local network around health and wellbeing and with the potential participation of 4 helix organisations in order to identify common interests for collaboration around jointly identified challenges with the digital tools as a lever. For this first session we invited around 120 people. 54 people filled the registration form and 46 people finally attended the session in person! It was a 90% success rate between the registered people and the attendances.

The session took 3h long and it was based on three main parts. The first one was dedicated to making an introduction and explanation of the EIC call expected outcomes and the INTEGER's aims. For the second part we created different subject tables and through co-creation methods

we tried to identify the needs and know-how from the different interested organisations. Finally, the third part of the event was focused on asking the attendees to sign the Letter of Intent (LOI) or Expression of Interest (here) that we previously created regarding the INTEGER project in order to register stakeholders' interest and commitment for further participation.

Second information session was held online on February 2nd 2023 for the people that could not attend the previous information physical session on Dec 13th. The session took just one hour long and was mainly focused on explaining about the Integer project as well as trying to involve more organisations through the LOI. We also took advantage to briefly introduce the digital Theglocal.Network platform that we were just building up for INTEGER 4H. For this second information session we invited a total of 74 people and finally 39 people attended the session. Due the session was held online; it was not necessary to previously fill a registration form.

Finally a total of 85 people from different 4 helix organisations attended both information sessions and between both information sessions we got a total of 49 signatures of the Expression of interest document. 27 in paper format and 22 in digital format.

Within the first physical session of the preparation phase on Dec 13th, as we explained. We run a co-creation session with all the participants splitted on different tables. Each table was focused on a specific subject with one inspiring case in order to facilitate the later questions and discussion.

For the Barcelona study visit session held on February 15th 2023 we basically envisaged a similar information and co-creation session as already tested on December 13th. Given the high number of initiatives and inspirational cases, it was decided to choose new ones to broaden the knowledge of the cases and to give the opportunity to new agents to present their ideas and projects.

The study visit was planned as an afternoon encounter between the local stakeholders together with all INTEGER partners. Therefore, we planned a number of added values for this first study visit:

1. The interaction between the local/regional level with the European level;
2. The promotion of the Col-laboratori initiative among regional stakeholders and the other participating regions in the project. One of the objectives of INTEGER is to dig on the regional innovation dynamics and collaborative endeavours;
3. The networking among different types of actors from each of the helices, from diverse fields and sectors and types of innovation with the aim to promote interpersonal, intercultural, interdisciplinary, intersectoral and international collaborations).

The session was run at the headquarters of the Catalan Agency for Public Health from the Catalanian Government. It was important to find a place that could concite the participation of all stakeholders taking into account that none of them should have a higher relevance over the others (this was explicitly taken into consideration as it was seen as a way to facilitate collaboration among stakeholders 'on equal foot').

The session was planned to ask the attendances to briefly introduce themselves and their organisations to the rest of the people. Previously, we had already created 5 different subject tables based on:

- the previous knowledge treasured by the responsible people leading the Col·laborari initiative at I2Cat Foundation;
- the information carved from the interests shown by relevant actors and
- a number of key social-driven initiatives related to the different domains identified by the World Health Organisation (WHO)

The table subjects were ageing, pollution, nutrition, social/labour inclusion and physical exercise.

To make the best of it we followed with a really short presentation about Integer 4H, due the main information was already explained in the previous sessions on Dec 13th and Feb 2nd.

After that the different European regions explained their own current situation regarding 4H collaborations within the health and wellbeing sectors.

Catalonia Region Stakeholders Mapping. The Catalonia region was explained by i2Cat Foundation starting with the inception of the the initiative Catalonia Col·laboratori for Health & Wellbeing, a first scientific paper on this issue has been published, deepening on the process, the lessons learned, identifying the principal themes for exploration in forthcoming research endeavours².

Fig. 1. Working groups in the INTEGER study visit in Barcelona

² Caro-Gonzalez, A. (2023). Towards a more inclusive triple transition and quadruple helix innovation ecosystems: the case of the Catalonian Col·laboratori on Health and Wellbeing within the INTEGER project. Special issue on the topic The design theory and practice from the perspective of humanities and social sciences: Interdisciplinary approaches. *Slovenský národopis*, 71 (3), 209–226. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31577/SN.2023.3.21> Available at: https://www.sav.sk/journals/uploads/11031553SN_2023_3_21.pdf

Fig. 2. Co-creation in the INTEGER study visit in Barcelona

2.3 Malopolska Study Visit

Two project partners representing Krakow Technology Park and the Jagiellonian University have been responsible for the organisation of the joint study visit to Krakow by the end of March 2023 according to the project timeline.

The aim of the study visit was to put in contact key social and digital business innovators who play a significant role and are vital actors in healthy living, active ageing policy and social exclusion areas in Krakow and Malopolska region. The study visit was planned for two days, 28 and 29 March 2023.

On the first day of study visit it was planned to give a general introduction to ageing policy in the city of Krakow and Malopolska. The ecosystem of startup-companies and innovators is boosting social innovation in the region. The role of research institutions and universities represented by Jagiellonian University (UJ) and its centre for technology transfer technology has been demonstrated during the morning session. The social needs and challenges as well as best practices developed and implemented in Krakow and Malopolska have been presented and widely discussed. The afternoon session was planned for an active workshop focused on identification of best practices and identifying common challenges and barriers for integration of social innovators with social activists and innovators on one side, and the technology providers on the other side.

The second day of study visit (29th March) was to give a deep dive into the ecosystem of wellbeing and health-oriented initiatives and businesses. The idea is to look for mechanisms of engaging and empowering social and technology driven business innovators to shape the bridge for fruitful collaboration. This translates the capability of KPT and UJ to effectively facilitate the dialogue with regional, national governments and on the EU level to deliver results in terms of creating models of social, digital, and business initiatives.

The intention of the joint workshop was to bring together participants representing 4H organisations, taking into consideration the variety of their activities and ecosystems they belong to. The stakeholders represent both social innovators, technology driven and digital innovators, but also public institutions, clusters, business support organisations and NGOs.

Thanks to participation in the workshop project partners representing two other local/regional innovation ecosystems from Catalonia in Spain and Hamburg region in Germany, it will be possible to establish a vibrant platform of sharing know-how, best practices and lessons learnt on implementation on social innovation supported by digital and business innovators.

Canvas methodology Day 1

On the first day of study there were both presentations and co-creation workshops. The experts' and stakeholder's presentations have been focused on showing the examples of ecosystem partners in the Małopolska region (including experience from Jagiellonian University, City of Krakow, local government and social innovators).

The workshop (with in total about 25 people) was a moderated discussion. The participants worked in smaller groups, and there was a forum summary after each round. The summaries have been recorded for later preparation of the summaries.

The main issues to be discussed during workshops were:

- Identification of best practices and lessons learnt.
- Identifying common challenges and barriers for integration of social innovators
- Connecting people to cross the silo model and bi-directional exchanges between social-driven and business-driven innovations
- Looking for joint synergies in 4H

Canvas methodology Day 2

The co creation session on day 2 (29th March) was focused on how social driven and business driven innovations can work together (identifying good examples), investigating what are the key obstacles in this field, and finding ways how Integer could act as a gate opener for this collaboration. The key questions to be asked during the session were:

- Name existing mechanisms/instruments/tools for connecting social-driven and business-driven innovations.
- What quadruple helix collaborations initiatives worth recommendation do you identify in Krakow/Malopolska?
- Do you know any Minimum Viable Products and/or Services for market and society within social innovation?
- What are the main challenges for quadruple helix collaborations in Krakow? What is missing?
- How can INTEGER and other similar projects support the regional innovators ecosystem?

Fig. 3. Group of co-creators in the INTEGER event in Krakow

Fig. 4. Working groups in the INTEGER study visit in Krakow

2.4 Hamburg Study Visit

The Hamburg study visit was structured in a way to find key stakeholders that could help to promote the project activities in the future and to give a good overview on existing activities in the region.

A key approach at the Hamburg regional study visit was to find ‘multiplying agents’ in the region. A short overview because the different stakeholders were selected:

Cluster Agency GWHH GmbH

The GWHH is a cluster agency owned by Hamburg's Chamber of Commerce and the Ministry of Social affairs. It is an important promoter in the healthcare sector with a network of about 3.000 members. The activities are focused on digitisation in the health sector, workforce, supporting start-ups and knowledge exchange between different sectors related to healthcare.

Mein Lido

Mein Lido is a good example of how civil society can support innovation in health care. The Max und Ingeburg Herz Foundation supported the start-up company Mein Lido that developed an App that allows people to connect with each other (including service providers and further facilities) in their own districts to support an independent living.

Working group sustainable city health

The working group is an already existing 4helic cooperation in the Hamburg region led by the civil society organisation Patriotische Gesellschaft. Stakeholders from the public administration, scientific, companies and the civil society are working on sustainability for better health in the Hamburg region.

Optimedis

The company developed a business model on how health systems can be organised in a more healthy and preventive way. It is working in different German and European regions with different systematic approaches and as well in several European innovation projects.

University hospital Hamburg-Eppendorf (UKE)

The UKE is one of the most important innovators in the healthcare sector in Hamburg. Innovation happens in different fields. In the study visit some examples were chosen, with the focus on collaboration and innovation.

Health harbour Hamburg / Philips

Philips DACH (GAS) founded the Health harbour Hamburg. The global player Philips gets in collaboration with local start-up companies, supports them with a special program and opens Philips infrastructure for these companies. This is an interesting approach on how global players and local start-ups can cooperate.

Fig. 5. Study visit in Hamburg

Fig. 6. Co-creation group in the study visit in Hamburg

2.5 Conclusions of the Study Visits

The plan for the three inter-regional study visits foresaw networking, collaborative, learning and exchanging actions at three different levels: local/regional, inter-regional and EU wider level.

Furthermore, the main important objectives were:

1. To identify complementarities and common interests between the INTEGER partners organisations.
2. To unveil if there exist effective mechanisms with capacity or potential to merge social-driven and business-driven innovations to close the gap (e.g., avoid the existing fragmentation and parallel developments build bi-directional bridges between social-driven and business-driven innovations);
3. To identify with stakeholders from the quadruple helix and the three regions the perceived opportunities and barriers towards enhancing more robust 4 helix collaborations (e.g., mind the gap between the knowledge triangle actors and civil engagement; promoting professionals and social entrepreneurs and social actors and citizens to be active part of the regional innovation agenda and funding mechanisms);
4. To uncover how INTEGER can support the different actors, regions and expected outcomes of the call.

3 STAKEHOLDERS EVENTS – Let’s Hack together!

In the dynamic landscape of the INTEGER project, Task 2.3 embarked on a strategic journey by orchestrating a pre-event to unite key stakeholders from the diverse regional ecosystems of Hamburg, Kraków, and Catalonia. This prelude paved the way for the subsequent online INTEGER Pre-Model Event on Healthy living and Social innovation, where stakeholders engaged in illuminating discussions to pinpoint challenges within the realms of healthy living and well-being. Leveraging a preliminary Google form survey, the event successfully identified three pivotal challenges, setting the stage for the transformative Innovation 4Healthy living | Let’s

Hack together! model event. This holistic approach epitomises INTEGER's commitment to cross-regional collaboration and innovative problem-solving within the 4Helix framework.

3.1 The Online Pre-Event

3.1.1 Goals and outcomes

As a first action in task 2.3 a pre-event was organised with the goal of gathering a group of identified key stakeholders from the 3Helix of the 3 regional ecosystems represented in the project, from Hamburg to Kraków and Catalonia, partners of INTEGER project. These regional stakeholders were invited by the INTEGER project to participate & contribute to an online INTEGER Pre-Model Event on Healthy living and Social innovation and to discuss and identify the main challenge in the healthy living and well-being ecosystem in their regions.

These key stakeholders were invited by INTEGER to be part of this focused first event to choose and propose 3 challenges to be discussed in the Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!, that will gather a wider group of stakeholders from the three regions. The key stakeholders come from the health and well-being ecosystems and were selected by the INTEGER partners, as the main player on their regional ecosystem, based on their experience and knowledge of the ecosystem of social innovation. One of the main criterias was their impact and experience in their sector in the region and in the overall ecosystem.

The key stakeholders event was the first event promoted between regional stakeholders in the INTEGER project, a first opportunity to start a conversation and engage directly with the main players of the regional ecosystems. This would also give the INTEGER partners the opportunity to benefit from these stakeholders' contributions and to kickstart a Col·laborathon that aimed to engage along the project stakeholders from the social innovation 3Helix in the sector of healthy living and well-being.

3.1.2 Before the online event

Prior to the online pre-event, the key stakeholders were invited to fill in a short Google form for the identification of a healthy living & well-being challenge in their region. The questions started by assessing their profile, as their sector and region and finally the identification of a main challenge in their region, based on topics identified in the study visits by INTEGER partners – same proposal to all regional partners.

The question presented about the challenge was: "What is, in your view, the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region? Taking into consideration physical, mental and social well-being." The options given to answer the question were presented in the table below.

What is, in your view, the biggest challenge/need in healthy living in your region? Taking into consideration physical, mental and social well-being.

1. Housing
2. Transportation
3. Food & Nutrition
4. Outdoor spaces & Buildings
5. Community support & Health services
6. Communication & Information

7. Civic participation & Employment
8. Social inclusiveness & Participation

Table 1. The options presented to the key stakeholders in the Google form pre-event regarding the challenge/need in their region in the healthy living & well-being ecosystem. In line with the WHO dimensions, the identification of the challenges, through their answers, helped the INTEGER project to assess the landscape and have a starting point of discussion during the online key stakeholders meeting, a pre-meeting before a wider stakeholders meeting. The Task 2.3 leader received the incoming replies and produced several graphics to be presented during the online meeting with the key stakeholders. The regional partners made the follow up along with F6S, on the reminders, answering additional questions and sending all needed information for the event participation. The key stakeholders were asked to appoint a representative with decision-making power to be present and participate in the pre-event for key stakeholders.

3.2 The Online Event

During the online event the INTEGER project was presented as well as the methodology of the event, the goal of this initiative as well as the way the INTEGER would use their input - to be used as a proposal of challenges for the stakeholders' event, in order to present solutions and brainstorm. The F6S presented the results of the Google form, namely the sector of work of the key stakeholders and their regions, as provided in annex 2, so that all participants could have an idea of the profile of the overall participants. Additionally, it was presented to the key stakeholders the selection of challenges, the most votes per region, based on the table one option, as well as per sector and per region. After this first presentation of the profile and choices of challenges per region, the main group of key stakeholders were divided into 3 groups, one subgroup per region, and were sent into breakout rooms. These small rooms served as a starting point to connect different stakeholders from the 4Helix of the regions giving them the opportunity to discuss the results of the Google form in their region and agree to present 1 (one) challenge that represents them. To reach this decision each subgroup had an appointed regional facilitator from the INTEGER project, allocated taking into consideration its regional familiarity. I2Cat facilitated the Catalonia subgroup, for example. The facilitator supported the moderation of the debate based on common guidelines that helped to reach a tangible and aligned result.

The methodology step implemented at this stage were:

1. Mapping of the relevant ecosystem actors and networks per region Catalonia (SP); Hamburg (GE); Krakow (POL) & internationally
2. Asking key stakeholders for inputs to identify common challenges and barriers from early stages for integration of social innovators into innovation in the healthy living and well-being ecosystem
3. Inviting to participate on a follow-up closed meeting in order to decide on 3 main challenges, per 3 subgroups divided regionally
4. Engaging the key stakeholders into a discussion, sharing experiences and views regionally and inter-regional facilitated by one regional representative (3 in total) of the INTEGER project

5. Inviting the key stakeholders to join the follow up event that would gather all stakeholders from the three different regions into a Col-laborathon model and have one spoke person presenting

The outcome of this first meeting was the definition of 3 challenges, identified regionally, to be discussed at a transregional & trans-sectoral level in the Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! that followed up. These were the 3 challenges selected by the subgroups:

- Kraków identified challenge (1): How to channel the unused potential of an ageing population in the regions, particularly in the cities?
- Hamburg identified challenge (2): Improve the lack of transparency & promote a better communication between sectors.
- Catalonia identified challenge (3): Health & wellness for Life. Specific but aligned actions to improve life quality.

The outcome of the event Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! was to present the 3 challenges identified for discussion to a wider audience that would gather more stakeholders from the 4 & 3Helix from the 3 regions. A collaboratory event, that was used as a first test on a model event, a learning process for the follow-up initiatives of INTEGER, named Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together!. The main aim of this follow-up event was to engage the 3Helix participants and to present solutions in the areas of health and well-being, to analyse the challenges beyond the regional view but in a trans-regional view.

3.2.1 Stakeholders Online Model Event

More than 20 active partners from the 3H and 4H in the three INTEGER participating regions were invited to participate in the model event, named by the project partners as Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! This event took place in two separate days, on the 17th and the 25th of May, 2023, online.

The objective of this event can be summarised into 4 objectives:

- Objective 1: Foster a culture of openness;
- Objective 2: Promote the use of collaborative platforms and networks to strengthen communication channels between the 4Helix;
- Objective 3: Encourage cross-sector partnerships & initiates towards social innovation;
- Objective 4: Enhance stakeholder engagement.

The Innovation 4Healthy living | Let's Hack together! Event, as mentioned previously, was divided into two online events, one meeting took place online on the 17th of May and a second and final event on the 25th of May. These two moments involve stakeholders from the quadruple helix from the healthy living ecosystem from the local/regional innovation ecosystems in the project: Catalonia (SP); Hamburg (GER) and Krakow (POL). These stakeholders were invited to gather and present transversal & replicable solutions to the challenges identified and selected by key stakeholders pre-event from the 4Helix in the healthy living ecosystem and based on their experience in their region. In between the two meetings the participants of the event were integrated in the INTEGER platform, where their profile was shared with the other participants, and they could follow up the conversations that started in the first session of the event on the 17th of May up until the 25th of May. However, they would still be part of the INTEGER platform if they wish in order to continue to be part of the process and participate in the following events and activities in the project. The idea of adding the

participants to the INTEGER platform was presented as an added value for the participants as being part of a vibrant ‘glocal’ community building long-term collaborations in physical, virtual or hybrid modes, along the project events and initiatives. This would be the main exploitation and sustainable action that would result from this task. The Innovation 4Healthy living | Let’s Hack together! is one important step in the several initiatives that INTEGER is implementing to build a 4Helix Col.laboratory model and to solve real problems with agents of the 4Helix in the 3 regions involved. All INTEGER regional partners were asked to invite between 20 to 35 stakeholders in their network.

4 OPEN LIVING LAB DAYS 2023

The INTEGER project was presented at the OpenLivingLab Days 2023. Hosted in Barcelona, this event brought together participants from around the world, fostering innovation and collaboration on a grand scale. One of the groundbreaking revelations was the introduction of the “col-laber.” The event featured a workshop titled “Towards a new generation of Living Labs,” which aimed to bridge the gap between social innovation and business-driven innovation by fostering collaboration among the agents of the quadruple helix. It is also important to highlight that the event marked a significant step forward in the mission to foster innovation and collaboration in the field of health and wellbeing. Representatives from various regions, including Catalonia, Hamburg, and Krakow, came together to co-create innovative solutions for societal challenges.

Fig. 7. Open Living Lab Days main page presenting the 2023 topic “Living Labs for an era of transitions”

5 INTEGER PLATFORM

The INTEGER platform was built up using existing digital full operating open tools, to interconnect the three regional innovation ecosystems and its main actors (social innovators,

entrepreneurs, investors, accelerators, tech oriented SMEs). Theglocal.network is designed to act as a focal point to share bottom-up co-identified social challenges Benefits of a virtual Community:

- Having an active virtual community attracts the interest of different agents (grants, sponsors, potential partners, suppliers, etc.) and it is in the management of these relationships that new ways of attracting resources for the organisation arise.
- Build participant loyalty by providing tangible benefits.
- It generates brand strength, visibility and loyalty. Belonging to a community that is active generates a lot of visibility for the organisation, the participants become brand ambassadors and create bonds of loyalty and belonging, generating a lot of notoriety in the environment.
- Becoming a member of theglocal.network in particular, benefits to an early access to contact details of local/regional partners, local/regional funding programmes, inspirational cases, activities, innovations, developments and networking opportunities
- Online international, regional or local inspirational meetings with INTEGER internal and external members through the glocal.network on (among others) the following topics:
 - The power of social innovation
 - Quality of life of citizens
 - Healthy living
 - Digitalisation
 - Profitable social innovation
 - (Social) Business development
- Forums in national languages on the INTEGER platform where members can meet and exchange (for mutual benefit)
- Templates and manuals for business development

The digital arenas and forums will be released in June 2023. The webinars and other activities will take place in September and beyond. The Platform is based on co-creation, involving different stakeholders collaborating with other participants in order to create and improve new products and services. Co-creation enables the whole group to also participate in the design process, beyond just listening to their ideas, thus empowering them to take part and work together.

Fig. 8. Integer Platform landing page

5.1 Key elements for managing the platform

To ensure proper use and effective management of the platform, a designated person must be responsible for managing and facilitating it. The dynamiser will be the person in charge of the correct management of the community, helping and guiding the members of the community, as well as stimulating their participation in the platform.

What are the ideal characteristics of a facilitator? A facilitator should possess good communication skills, initiative to carry out creative and innovative activities, knowledge of social media, familiarity with the working space, and the ability to stimulate and engage with people. The role of a facilitator is to bring these qualities to the job. The individual in charge of community dynamisation will play a crucial role in shaping users' perception of the platform. They must take actions that affect the emotional, affective, and social aspects, while also serving as the primary point of contact for users seeking support and information.

Why is it necessary to energise a virtual community? Because the community has general needs, such as finding new ways to generate resources for the organisation, observing how the community participates, collaborates, learns and communicates, and attracts stakeholders to increase the organisation's visibility. There is a need for the development and promotion of interesting projects and opportunities. Additionally, there is a need for quick and easy access to information and the ability to share it. It is also important to have valuable information presented with data and graphics.

Before starting to develop the platform, it was essential to define certain aspects, such as the conceptual strategic framework and the aims and objectives. Knowing the aims will help us focus on both the community and monitoring, ensuring that they are aligned with the goals to be achieved.

5.1.1 Related to content and its dissemination

Our ability to identify, structure, publish and distribute content and resources of potential interest to our community members will determine the added value to the user of being part of the community.

- Resources/Information: To achieve the most powerful digital space in terms of information about the organisation and all that surrounds it, and to make it a differential reference. Coordinate a powerful system for identifying resources and uploading content for each thematic area.
- Trends hunters of relevant information: Disseminating this information through various channels. Visits to other countries, attracting relevant people, etc.
- Dissemination: Looking for the most viral creative content: Designing creative content that highlights the value of the organisation to try to viralise it through the different channels (it can be of any type). Positioning of the organisation and dissemination and promotion of the ecosystem created around it.

5.1.2 Related to participation and management and collaboration

The task of actively participating through actions in the management of users is very important to ensure that each member of the network is able to find in the platform a tool that brings them value.

It is in this task that we will be largely responsible for the role that person will take on as a user of our community. In fact, it is up to the management to demonstrate to the user that he/she is part of a community and that he/she will receive personalised treatment, updated at all times according to his/her interests/needs, and that he/she will be offered solutions to his/her concerns.

5.2 Some key actions to encourage stakeholder participation in the platform

Get to know our users

It is interesting to manage all users through campaigns targeted at the types of users we have previously defined and used for recruitment. Thanks to this segmentation and the targeting of campaigns to these segments, we will be able to optimise the work of dynamisation. In this way, we will be able to meet the needs of several users with the same actions and generate significant experiences. The nature of the tasks to be carried out should always be in line with the nature of the information that we have been able to record on each of the agents that make up our network, i.e. the file that we have completed on each of the users of our ecosystem.

Welcome message on the platform

It is advisable to send a personalised welcome message to each person who registers on the platform. It is advisable to use this first message to make it easier for the user to enter into the dynamics of the platform from the moment they register.

Attract community agents with the potential to support the dynamisation of the community

In this way we can provide them with spaces for connection and interaction with the ecosystem and they will be able to support the dynamisation of the community by adding value to it and in the same way they themselves can also achieve recognition and the generation of a community around their issues of interest.

Spreading news about your organisation

The registered person is a representative of their own organisation or of one of which they are a member, they will find great value in us being able to monitor and disseminate all the news referring to their organisation. This monitoring task is possible thanks to a follow-up of your organisation's RRSS or thanks to Google Alerts, to subsequently publish and disseminate this news in a relevant channel or conversation group, RRSS, etc. and also to establish a relationship between the news we have published with the profile as a professional or organisation created on the platform.

Disseminate an event created by your organisation or in which he/she participates

Encouraging participation in a conference or other type of event promoted by the organisation of one of our users or in which our user participates is another way to increase the loyalty of this person in the community

Personalised invitation to an event or conference: Knowing what a user is interested in or needs makes it easier for us to invite them to events, conferences, etc. that may be useful or attractive to them.

Sending news and articles specific to your sector

Offering information from experts in the user's field is a good strategy for increasing their knowledge and letting them know that we know what they like and are interested in. This type of activity can be done through regular mailings, sporadic messages on an individual basis, etc. Depending on what we

Sending information about grants that can help them meet their needs or achieve their professional goals

Being aware of and personally informing them of calls for grants or programmes that could help them to succeed in their projects or achieve the goals that a particular member of our ecosystem has set for themselves.

Contacting other members of the community

Acting as an intermediary to introduce agents who are members of our network and get them to expand their network of contacts, meet their professional needs, collaborate, etc.

- Invitation to subscribe to a specific channel
- Invitation to join a specific discussion group
- Show them how to improve their presence and positioning on the platform
- Presenting the system as a tool that helps to strengthen their presence in the network or community.

Facilitate responses

Everyone should feel that they are being listened to and that the community is a place where there is always someone who can provide solutions to their concerns.

Encourage user identification with the community

People value and appreciate when they feel part of something. This sense of belonging makes us feel comfortable and confident in the environment. Therefore, the facilitator must ensure that the user sees the community as a useful space, that each of the people who make up the

community is part of a space in which they can interact, and that it is the place to which they turn regularly.

5.3 Definition, monitoring and evaluation of dynamisation

In addition to the above, we need to consider the monitoring of the same through an evaluation system, which will be carried out through reports and the monitoring that the administrator can carry out from the administration panel. And to put all this into practice, we need to communicate the importance of making the community dynamic. To do this, we need to ask ourselves the following questions:

Why would someone enter the community tomorrow, does he/she have something to do there?

We need to create spaces where users have questions to ask, for which we recommend the strategy of starting with small groups of different types of users of the community, offering them questions to ask and achieve in the community, and thus, group by group, achieving a larger community. In other words, recruit the community in differentiated phases, taking into account users with similar needs or concerns, consolidate this group and continue with others. Taking into account the specifics of each community, this can vary significantly both in terms of the size of the groups and the launch strategy.

Fig. 9. Information in numbers of the INTEGER platform TheGlocal.network

6 REGIONAL COL-LABORATHONS

6.1 Catalonia Col-laborathon

Fig. 10. Working groups in the INTEGER Col-laborathon in Catalonia

Number of inscriptions: 76

Number of participants: 55

The Catalonia Col-laborathon, part of the innovative INTEGER project, was an extraordinary day of collaboration, innovation, and collective learning. During the event, six initiatives and projects were presented, standing out for their commitment to sustainable development, health, and well-being in the community. The event took place on November 22nd and lasted the entire day.

One of the most notable initiatives was led by Oriol Huguet and carried out by the Ajuntament de Vilanova i la Geltrú with support from the Diputació de Barcelona. This project focuses on promoting emotional well-being among youth, creating a bridge between them and the local resources available for their well-being.

The FoodCLIC project, under the leadership of Rosina Malagrida from LivingLab IrsiCaixa, is another example of innovation. It focuses on healthy and sustainable eating in the neighbourhoods of the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona, receiving support from European and local projects, and showing a strong commitment to community health and food sustainability.

In the field of well-being for the elderly, the VR360 project, led by David Gateu from Valls Genera, offers an immersive and sensory experience through virtual reality, allowing older people to virtually explore natural environments, an initiative that innovatively merges technology and social care.

Albert Munne introduced us to Memima Baby, an app dedicated to musical education for babies. This tool allows parents to introduce their children to the world of music, fostering not only musical skills but also language development and creativity.

Marta Rofin from Bax & Company introduced the Healthy Cities Generator, an online tool that assesses the health impact of urban planning. This project, selected as the most outstanding at

the Col-laborathon, offers us an innovative and practical vision of how to improve health and well-being through urban design.

Karina Simieli presented SeniorLab, a platform for redefining and co-creating services and products focused on an increasingly ageing society. This project stands out for its inclusive and collaborative approach, seeking to involve people of all ages in the design and development process.

The event's workshops, based on the SOAR methodology, the Social Innovation Canvas, provided alternatives for funding and replicability strategies, offering participants a space for debate, reflection, and collective creation. These workshops were at the heart of the event, where ideas were transformed into action plans and implementation strategies.

The talks at the event, like those by Maite Fibla from Ship2B Ventures and Adrià Buzón from Cuideo, were highlights, providing valuable perspectives on the financing of impact projects and business strategies for genuine social impact.

Finally, the event closed with a pitch contest where the evolution of the projects throughout the day could be observed, and the winning project was selected.

Evaluators provided constructive feedback on the presented initiatives, pointing out both potential and areas for improvement. They generally highlighted the appreciation of innovation and the potential impact of the initiatives, emphasising the importance of replicability and sustainability. They acknowledged the reliance of some initiatives on public entities and warned of the challenges this may present. They also highlighted the need to include population segments that might not have access to necessary technology.

On the other hand, they valued the ability of certain initiatives to address cross-cutting problems and generate significant social impact. However, concerns persist about long-term viability in terms of costs and maintenance of these solutions. They also emphasised the need for clearer impact measurement to assess the real effectiveness of the initiatives.

In conclusion, the assessment suggests a balance between praise for creativity and a call to attention to practical aspects such as financial sustainability and universal accessibility, as well as precision in evaluating results.

The attendees' assessment was overwhelmingly positive, highlighting the relevance of the event in achieving the proposed objectives. Participants particularly emphasised the value of the connections made, the inspiration, and the knowledge gained. Although there were suggestions for improving future editions, such as the need for more time for networking, the event was perceived as a significant step towards promoting social and digital innovation in Catalonia.

The Catalonia Col-laborathon became a catalyst for innovative ideas and projects, with Marta Rofin's Healthy Cities Generator selected as the standout project. This project offers a promising and practical approach to improving urban health and well-being. We will delve deeper into this winning project, with a presentation from one of its promoters, Josep Biosca, exploring its implications and potential to transform our cities into healthier and more sustainable environments.

The attendees' assessment of the Catalonia Col-laborathon reflected a generally positive appreciation, underscoring the relevance and effectiveness of the event in reaching the proposed goals. Participants especially noted the value of the connections made, the inspiration, and the knowledge acquired throughout the day. This was particularly significant as it demonstrates the event's effectiveness in fostering collaboration and idea exchange among the various participants.

The Col-laborathon was seen as a valuable and relevant initiative for the region, marking a significant step towards the development of innovative social and digital projects in Catalonia. The event served not only as a forum for presenting projects and discussing ideas but also as a platform for forming strategic alliances and fostering a more robust innovation ecosystem.

Attendees left with a feeling of satisfaction and enthusiasm for future initiatives that will arise from this experience of collaboration and creativity. The positive feedback from participants demonstrates the event's success in achieving its goals and sets an optimistic precedent for future collaborations and innovation events in the region.

6.2 Malopolska Col-laborathon

Fig. 11. Co-creation groups in the INTEGER Col-laborathon in Krakow

Krakow Technology Park and Jagiellonian University, in collaboration with the Life Science Krakow Cluster created a unique event that served as a platform for collaboration among students, older persons, business professionals, administrators, and academic individuals. Using scientific terminology, it brought together actors in what is known as the quadruple helix. The AHathon (in the project terminology “regional Col-laborathon”) and the LifeScience Open Space conference, mentioned here, took place at the KPT headquarters from **November 29th to December 1st**. On Friday, the winners of the three-days event were announced. Excellent ideas, outstanding presentations, and excellent collaboration impressed the jury. Starting from

the innovation ideas and solutions addressed to active health ageing, the winning main prize team is mentored and supported in creating their MVP and testing it with end users in one of the municipalities of Malopolska region.

Fig. 12. AHATHon Banner

Regional Col-laborathon

Krakow Technology Park, traditionally associated with technological innovations, has ventured into a new area – social innovations. Drawing on the KPT’s experience of organising many hackathons, events for creators, or programmers, the concept was successfully combined with the opportunity to work on social innovations in the field of ageing challenges. The second partner on the Polish side is the Center for Evaluation and Analysis of Public Policy at the Jagiellonian University (JU), whose experience in social innovations’ projects and their evaluations ensured the high quality of the research approach and collaboration between innovators, explaining the idea behind the work during the event and as well being in practice with moderating and facilitating the team works, as well in helping with inviting speakers for the event.

AHA, the main change in the traditional understanding of a hackathon, is an acronym for "Active Healthy Ageing." During the three days of work, teams consisting of both young and older individuals worked on social innovations to address real problems. Most participants focused on communication issues (between generations) but also with lack of adequate and relevant information for older groups of people and whether there is enough access of information (cultural, sports, local) for older persons and transportation limitations from some parts of the region. One team emphasised the need for developing the idea of gratitude (every day) as – scientifically confirmed – important for the overall good quality of life and so with impact on the well-being.

AHATHon was a great event which resulted in five excellent innovative ideas of projects, responding to the challenge of “How to effectively take advantage of the benefits of an ageing society, especially in the context of urban regions?”, presented to a wide audience on the third day.

Only thanks to the commitment to the international project and well-established partnerships within the INTEGER project, such interesting things could happen. During the

event KPT and UJ used the knowledge gathered within the project to conduct the Col-laborathon and to adjust of the col-laboratory model and its role in the regional ecosystem. All those data and lessons learnt have made a significant impact for the event conducted in Krakow.

As mentioned above, during that event the Krakow team was able to present the collaboration model (established within the project) to all vital regional stakeholders during the meeting (took place 30th November) of the so-called Special Interest Group of Active Healthy Aging (SIG AHA). The meeting was very fruitful with many insights of how to make that model event better and more suitable for the regional context.

The SIG Meeting's theme was "In search of the next generation of innovation labs (Living Labs) for health and quality of life." Participants discussed systemic support for social innovators so that their social projects have organisational and financial continuity. During the workshop, a model of cooperation prepared by the Integer project was presented, discussed with the participants, and recommendations were collected to adapt the model to the needs of our region in further activities.

The SIG Meeting included the following thematic areas:

1. The introduction into SIG AHA – Special Interest Group: Active Healthy Ageing
2. The experience of the region: different experiences of regional actors in the field of senior citizen policy (challenges, best practices etc)
3. Discussion about INTEGER Model:
 - discussion on possible shortcomings of the model,
 - discussion on the inclusion of such elements as: trust, business and technological competence (social innovator), common, developed goal, systems thinking, right to fall.
4. Recommendations:
 - not to waste money on the same problems; rather, to maintain sustainability or on more specific activities
 - declining care capacity (challenge: care service, assistant service)

Healthy Habits Conference

The AHATHon also became a part of a larger event organised in the capital of Małopolska for several years, namely the Life Science Open Space. In the Lifestyle session, hosted by the Krakow Technology Park, we could hear many inspiring presentations, ranging from growing plants in specially adapted home cabinets to issues faced by shift workers and the challenges of venereal diseases.

One of the panel "The Power of Habit as the Best Prescription for a Healthy Life," participants learned about the successful stories of for example how sports and medical professionals deal with being healthy and their approach to building a healthy and happy life. The wide range of presentations and lectures only demonstrates how the integration of various areas of activity and different environments has become crucial for our lifestyle.

The main motto of the Lifestyle Pitch session was: **The power of habit is the best recipe for a healthy life!** During the discussions after pitch sessions a talk was carried out about food and environmental innovations that affect our lifestyles. Keynote speeches and discussions that

inspired us to live healthier and more sustainable lives, as well as an opportunity to forge new partnerships. The LIFESTYLE session was moderated by Natalia Bursiewicz, the president of the Krakow Technology Park. And there was also the special guest of the session – a well known lifestyle expert in Poland – Ms Katarzyna Bosacka, TV journalist and author of books on a wide range of healthy lifestyles.

Facts and Fig. about Col·laborathon and conference

This three-day event, gathering **more than 200 participants**, once again demonstrated the significance of collaboration, not only in organising events but also in creating a platform or meeting place for people for whom meeting under normal circumstances is often impossible. Thanks to the conference and AHATHon, the Krakow Technology Park and Jagiellonian University in collaboration with the LifeScience Krakow Cluster Foundation, proved that such a concept of joint collaboration makes the development of the further collaboration and partnership very promising and effective, with ideas to promote in future.

During the regional Col·laborathon **5 teams** (of 4 to 7 people) worked for **3 consecutive days** on their ideas. The final pitches took place on a stage and gathered a wide audience (on the third day). There has been one winner – a project called **SąsiadeX** and four equal prizes. And the decision of the Jury was that all teams got the financial reward and the winning team was offered additionally the special dedicated mentoring and a possibility of implementation activities as the next step of their project. It should be emphasised here, that thanks to the joint effort of the organisers, the teams of different ages were formed to ensure interdisciplinarity and diversity of perspectives. The age range of teams included people aged 23-82.

6.3 Hamburg Col·laborathon

Fig. 13. Networking at the INTEGER Col·laborathon in Hamburg

Number of inscriptions: 21 (public administration, economy, university, civil society) + 6 start-up pitches

Start-up Pitches

The Hamburg Col-laborathon was divided into two workshops and two start-up pitches. 6 start-up companies presented their innovative health solutions in two pitches October 11 and November 22 2023. A jury consisting of Kai Schnackenberg, Kai Fritze, and Marcus Falke rated the pitches regarding the categories Criteria & score system:

As a starting point for the evaluation overall, the proposals, if they are not a new project from the start, they have to present novelty and innovation. It may already have a working base, with running actions, however as a proposal it has to present novelty that can be at a strategic level, tools or implementation level, or other, in order to justify the need for support. The 3 main criteria have the same height and are to be assessed on the proposal to be scored from 01 to 05 by the external evaluators are the following:

Concept and innovation

Participants must demonstrate a clear set of objectives aligned with the definition of the goals and with the general objectives of the INTEGER project and the Col-laborathon challenge. Appropriateness of the project scope as the overall project vision. Quality, credibility, and clarity of project description. Interoperability level of the proposed solution. Innovation level, not only in a technical perspective, but also in a strategic and implementation perspective, as well as practices.

Sustainability and replicability

Quality, effectiveness and clarity of project activities and its sustainability & replicability. Alignment of the activities/actions with the INTEGER goals and the SDG. Presentation of milestones and means of verification.

Impact

The proposal must define its ambition and a clear set of expectations aligned with the objectives of the Col-laborathon. Proposals must demonstrate the impact of the proposal and its contribution. The ambition underlines the potential extent and overall impact of the proposal actions.

After rating the pitches, the start-up company “**help**” had received the highest scoring of all and was declared winner of the Hamburg pitch contest.

First Col-laborathon

The first workshop took place on October 6th and was held online. In this workshop the stakeholders of the Hamburg region addressed their needs and expectations towards the Hamburg Living Lab but also the 2nd workshop that was planned as the main event of the Hamburg Col-laborathon. The stakeholders had a common understanding, that the Col-laborathon needs to address the Hamburg ecosystem and that the success of the INTEGER project in Hamburg is closely connected to developing a concrete vision of what the goal of the Hamburg Living Lab will be. The need of getting practical examples from successful Living Labs was also expressed by the stakeholders.

Second Col-laborathon

The second workshop was a full day presence workshop on 3rd November in a representative location in Hamburg.

The event started with inputs about federal and state initiatives on social innovation; speakers from the Hamburg Ministry for Economy and Innovation from the IFB Investment and Development Bank Hamburg outline relevant policies and support programmes to foster social innovation.

Meeting the stakeholders' needs to get practical examples of successful Living Labs, the event went on with three best practice presentations by Living Lab representatives from Bremen, Siegen and Barcelona (online).

In the afternoon, the stakeholders were divided into two groups, with the 4 helixes represented in both groups. In the groups, the participants discussed the following key questions and documented them on flipcharts:

- What added value can a Living Lab bring to the participating persons/organisations?
- How could a Hamburg Living Lab be organised?
- What resources are available and what other resources are needed?
- How can these resources be provided?

The aim was to develop a common understanding of what a Living Lab in Hamburg should look like. The added value of a Living Lab for each organisation was discussed in order to encourage stakeholder involvement in the development of Living Lab. By looking together at possible structures and available resources, the participants developed and agreed on the next steps that need to be taken for the implementation of a Living Lab in Hamburg.

Results documentation of the Workshop

Working group 1:

Added value of a Living Lab in Hamburg: In order to generate added value, a needs analysis in the form of a survey must be carried out in advance. The added value that can then arise is as follows:

- Low-threshold offers for citizens in the neighbourhood
- Opportunity to introduce problem-oriented projects
- A discussion channel where different people can exchange ideas, but where specific issues can also be raised
- Platform to introduce topics but also as a "door opener"
- How a Hamburg Living Lab can be organised:
 - It is important that the Living Lab builds on existing structures
 - Neighbourhood based

Working group 2:

Added value of a Hamburg Living Lab can only be successfully generated if the Living Lab is very specific and located in a district (Leibniz Living Lab Bremen as a model). If these conditions are met, the following added value can result:

- Better and trustful access to target groups; bottom-up approach
- Sustainable structure (in contrast to projects)
- Networking opportunities
- The LL as a sustainable "vessel" from which projects originate but not a project itself
- Important structures:

- Start with networking within the district, don't start too big
- Pay attention to new players (possibly with private capital)
- An unbiased view from the outside is necessary
- Financing:
 - An exploratory phase is necessary (in this phase, possibly find preliminary projects, partners, check constellations for cooperation). The exploratory phase could be financed by a foundation.
 - Should have many opportunities to try things out. However, this is difficult with public funds. Private funding should therefore be considered (e.g. foundations and private investors)

After the two working group presentations, the whole group started a fruitful discussion about how to concretely move on from this point. In the discussion, the following points were covered:

- The Poliklinik Veddel is currently setting up a district laboratory with researchers. They are already integrated into the district and are being partially funded.
- There are six local health centres in Hamburg. These probably do not have the resources to set up an LL. However, they could be used as partners because they address a specific target group.
- Initially, corporations should only be with few selected players so that the project does not grow too quickly.
- Cooperation with a large number of health insurance companies should be avoided. In general, one should limit oneself to a few selected investors, as otherwise everyone will want to have a say.
- The INTEGER project can help the Hamburg stakeholders to lead the LL into an exploratory phase. This must be set at 2-3 years.
- Be careful with double structure: there already are several networks. The LL needs to stand out and have an individual focus

The result of the discussion was that the following next steps were planned:

- Regular digital meetings but also meetings in person
- Agree on short and medium-term goals and milestones together
- Create a joint roadmap at the next meeting
- Next meeting second half of January
- MLHSA sends invitation for the next meeting and shares the workshop documentation with all participants
- It is recommended to subscribe to the project platform “The Glocal Network” (<https://integer4h.theglocal.network/>) for further cooperation work.

7 GRAND FINALE INTERREGIONAL COL-LABORATHON

On January 17, 2024, the INTEGER Col-laborathon reached its conclusion, marking a collaborative and innovative journey involving 28 participants in an online event.

Lina Silveira from F6S facilitated the event and handed over the floor to Xiaoni Li (Universitat Rovira i Virgili), who provided insights into WP3 goals and main tasks. Toñi Caro, the project coordinator from i2CAT, shared the Col-laborathon model, and Rafel Nulart (i2CAT) presented the platform, referred to as a "digital participatory space." This session included a summary of the regional events previously held in the three ecosystems: Catalonia (Xiaoni Li), Krakow (Mateusz Kowacki - Krakow Technology Park), and Hamburg (Kai Schnackenberg - The Ministry of Social Affairs of the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg).

The winning projects from each ecosystem were presented as follows:

- Healthy Cities Generator - Bax & Company - from Catalonia (Celia Garcia): Introducing a tool focusing on urban health and wellbeing, the Healthy Cities generator.
- Sąsiadex from Krakow (Tomasz Rębkowski): Revolutionising car sharing for commuting individuals, aiding older adults in Poland.
- Start-up company help from Hamburg (Annika Bruhns-Petersson and Antje Kallweit): Presenting digital pain therapy through an innovative app.

Attendees explored alternative financing strategies with powerful insights from Josep Biosca of the SHIP2B Foundation while evaluators selected winners based on Concept & Innovation, Sustainability & Replicability, and Impact. Congratulations to the winner, Healthy Cities Generator! The INTEGER team will provide the winner's label and accolades to finalists, reaffirming our commitment to supporting development and fundraising. Special congratulations to all finalists for their outstanding efforts.

Xiaoni Li concluded the session with final notes and lessons learned, highlighting that "The regional events worked as a collaborative learning hub. The events allowed the regions to find common ground and share insights and lessons learned that will support each region to adjust and implement their programs in their regions." Join the project on our platform, INTEGER Platform, where you can connect with like-minded organisations, explore networking opportunities, and engage in social innovation projects tackling real challenges alongside the 4 helix stakeholders.

8 CONCLUSION

The inter-ecosystem learning process is a central element for the success of the INTEGER project. The various steps were necessary and serve as the basis for further cooperation.

During the study visits, a shared comprehension of the innovation ecosystems has been cultivated and a significant number of 4 Helix actors have been acquainted with. The enhancement of communication among regions and peers in the 4 Helix focusing on the healthy living and well-being domain has initiated an awareness campaign regarding common needs in the economic and social innovation ecosystems. This marks the initial phase of increased interregional exchange.

The Stakeholder events were the start of developing a peer-to-peer approach to joint digital actions in order to support social innovation entrepreneurs and start-ups and open them to a larger network, beyond their region to other social innovation SMEs, investors, corporates and

other actors within the healthy living and well-being area ecosystem that could provide direct support or benefit from their innovation. It has been important to identify champions and early adopters, stakeholders with a vision aligned with INTEGER. These actors have expressed their commitment with time and active participation to support in early stages of defining the INTEGER Model.

The INTEGER platform serves as the foundation for all inter-ecosystem exchanges. It is a crucial tool facilitating the exchange of ideas, collaboration, and project development among 4 Helix partners from various regions and beyond. This platform provides innovations with an open space and broadens the project's engagement to include a wider array of stakeholders.

Finally the Col-laborathons were important processes for introducing the findings from the innovation structures of the partner regions in their own ecosystem and working on implementation strategies with the stakeholders. In Hamburg, for example, the examples of the living labs from Krakow and Barcelona were used to develop an idea of what can be adopted in the local ecosystem in order to strengthen local innovation capacity.

At the final event, these processes from the partner regions were brought together again and a joint vision was developed on how innovative ecosystems can be promoted more strongly in the future.

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